

Collaborative Socio-Ecological Systems Research: A web-based, interactive data mapping and analysis system for integrated research and community engagement

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SESTRA-RIMS: A Community-Informed Platform for Natural and Social Systems Data Integration

The Arctic and sub-Arctic are experiencing unprecedented climate-induced environmental change alongside substantial social, economic, and institutional changes. The regional water cycle is undergoing rapid transformations as a consequence of complex interactions of multiscale drivers and feedbacks. Considering the critical role of water and water resources, hydroclimatological changes coupled with globalization and other socioeconomic transitions have already significantly impacted many riverine communities in cold regions. To better understand these changes and provide comprehensive assessment of the complex interactions between environmental and human processes in cold regions, we developed a collaborative project “Socio-Ecological Systems Transformations in the pan-Arctic: Climate Change Impacts on Riverine Communities” (SESTRA Project, www.sestra-rivers.org). Focusing our research on two diverse river basins, Kuskokwim and Selenge, located in less studied parts of Alaska and Eurasia (Mongolia), this project analyzes the complex and dynamic linkages between different components of the changing hydroclimatological and social systems to improve our understanding of socio-ecological system (SES) interactions, assess their combined impact on human well-being, and co-develop current and future adaptation options with local communities.

The development of cyberinfrastructure for publicly accessible data and project materials is a key project goal. We have been developing a user-friendly online Rapid Integrated Mapping and analysis System for the SESTRARIMS project (SESTRARIMS) that will allow its users to submit, integrate and analyze various types of geospatial information, navigate through common climatic, hydrological, environmental, and social data over the study regions and over entire pan-Arctic domain.

SESTRARIMS online mapping and analysis system has already integrated more than 50 Tb of data over a variety of themes such as climate, hydrology, land cover and land use, and human dimensions. The data include: numerous remote sensing products (e.g., MODIS, LANDSAT imagery providing important information on snow, surface temperature, freeze-thaw, soil moisture, water storage); multiple spatial/temporal climate fields based on observations (UDEL, CRU) and model/assimilation-based (e.g., NCEP, ERA5, MERRA-2, multiple CMIP-5/6 GCM outputs); simulation results from a range of spatial/temporal regional climatic (e.g. Weather Research Forecasting (WRF) model), hydrological (UNH Water Balance Model (WBM)) and permafrost models (e.g. Geophysical Institute Permafrost Laboratory model (GIPL)) generated by prior and ongoing projects; and auxiliary data (e.g., land cover maps, river networks, soil maps, etc.). In addition to gridded data the system can include various station/point network datasets such as meteorological (air temperature, precipitation, humidity, etc.), hydrological (e.g. river discharge, water temperature, river ice thickness), permafrost (active layer thickness, soil temperature etc.), socio-economic data (e.g. demography, population density, household size and composition, prices/cost of living, occupations and sectors, access to education and health services, etc.). These point/station data are useful to validate gridded fields of modeled and remotely sensed data.

The current SESTRARIMS instantiation has many useful features for research, exploration and understanding the dynamics of these complex regional socio-ecological systems. In addition to visualization and mapping, SESTRARIMS contains web services designed for digital data content accessibility (Appendix, Figure 1):

- i) A dataset search service among our data holdings, including more than 15 000 raster and vector datasets with daily and other temporal resolution time series and single layer data in 200+ geospatially referenced file formats supported by the open source GDAL library.
- ii) The ability to view different temporal aggregation subsets of the same time series data (e.g. daily, monthly, yearly, daily climatology or long-term means) as well as their spatial aggregations over both physical (watershed) and social (national, sub-national) administrative units.
- iii) Instant access to the underlying raw data values for each pixel of the client-side displayed maps.
- iv) On-line interactive computation and creation of new data layers via the Geospatial data calculator tool that operates across spatial and temporal dimensions to perform algebraic,

logical, or simple scripting functions over an arbitrary number of RIMS mounted datasets and their time series layers.

v) Tools for easy mounting and management of vector, raster, point/station data, and their metadata.

vii) A vector polygon tool allowing a user to draw free-hand polygons or select upstream areas of river networks for data spatial aggregation and analysis, e.g. using the Geospatial data calculator.

Detailed description of SESTRA-RIMS including map navigation, view control, data visualization and analysis is provided in comprehensive online instructions.

SESTRA-RIMS as a User-Focused Platform

The SESTRA-RIMS system is still being developed and improved in collaboration with users to better meet the needs of regional and local stakeholders. For example, future system upgrades will include user (public) and superuser (project team scientists) login options allowing interactive session tools similar to those of the Environmental Response Management Application (ERMA) developed at UNH (Jacobi et al. 2009) and widely used by NOAA (ERMA 2014) and other organizations.

The current web system front-end has been developed in English primarily for the Alaskan users and later it will be duplicated in Mongolian for users in the Selenge and adjacent river basins and into an easy-to-use format for community members, policymakers, and local decision-makers.

The platform was introduced during training workshops in Mongolia (Appendix, Figure 2) to demonstrate various system operability and teach, in an interactive way, how to use the basic functionality of the system for regional and local data query and analysis. The workshops generated great interest and relevant feedback from local environmental specialists from the Ministry of Emergency Situations, Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of Health, Construction and Urban Development and Water Management Agencies, Hydrometeorological Service, as well as geography teachers from several local high schools who found that the SESTRA-RIMS has very useful educational applications. This and other workshop outcomes will be used to adapt the system to the needs and priorities of regional and local decision-makers and educators.

SESTRA-RIMS as an Interactive User-Inspired Tool

SESTRA-RIMS is designed as a user-inspired research tool that supports data co-development with communities through participatory research (Nadeau et al. 2022; Weber-Pillwax 2009). By

engaging communities as research partners in data production and validation, the platform is grounded in local realities, reflects community priorities, and produces results that are actionable. This partnership approach strengthens community data integration, builds local capacity to interpret findings, and enables communities to apply SESTRARIMS decision-support outputs in real-world planning and management. The co-production process also strengthens trust and local capacity, producing actionable, practically oriented science that remains aligned with community needs while being directly useful to decision-makers.

Decision-relevant information can be delivered as maps depicting community vulnerability to future hydroclimatic change, alongside region-specific adaptation, mitigation, and management options for sustainable development under multiple pathways. In this way, SESTRARIMS has strong potential to empower communities by enhancing the capacity of policymakers and local decision-makers through interactive decision-support outputs.

Acknowledgement

This research was funded by the U.S. National Science Foundation, Project Socio-Ecological Systems Transformation in River basins of the sub-Arctic under climate change (SESTRARIMS), award # 2318380, 2318381, 2318382.

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Appendix.

The screenshot displays the SESTRARIMS web interface. At the top, it features logos for NSF, UNH, UAF, and UNI, along with the title 'Mapping and Data Analysis System For SESTRA project'. Below the header, there are several functional panels:

- Dataset ID:** A search bar for datasets with options for 'Point Data' and 'Dataset DB (optional)'. Buttons for 'Search DB', 'Update Map', and 'Reset' are present.
- Available Datasets:** A section with a 'Data Menu' containing 'Raster & Polygon Data' and 'Dataset Search'.
- Dataset and Map Options:** Includes 'Select Projection' (Geographic, Polar, Pseudo-Mercator), 'Raster Data Resample' (Nearest Neighbour, Bilinear, Lock), and 'Dynamic Styling Options' (Update Map with Dynamic Style, Reset).
- Point Data:** A section with a 'Use Point Control' instruction and a green button.
- Overlays:** Checkboxes for 'Admin.', 'Bing', 'OSM', 'N Rivers', 'M Rivers', 'Hydro', and 'Graticule'.
- Map View:** A map of the Arctic region showing temperature data. A 'Choose Temporal Resolution' dialog is open, showing options for 'Yearly Climatology', 'Monthly Climatology', and 'Daily Climatology'. Two data popups are visible: one for 'Lena' (113.623 59.958) and one for 'Indigirka' (146.874 67.438).
- The Map Data Calculator:** A section for performing mathematical and logical functions. It includes a table of input datasets (Elev, Bath, NPP60, RootDepth, SoilPH, NDVI) and a 'Pixel Equation' field. Buttons for 'Do Calculations', 'Reset', and 'Last Calculation Info/Download' are provided.
- The Vector Polygon Tools:** A section for selecting regions by polygons. It includes a 'Number of polygons: 1' indicator, a 'List of User Selected Polygons' button, and a legend for 'Polygons selected for the analysis' and 'Polygons selected for the deletion'.

Figure 1: SESTRARIMS front page (<https://sestra.unh.edu>) and basic functionality of the system. Current basic features of the System include: 1) data search/selection; 2) pixel query tool (i-tool); 3) time series navigation tool; 4) tool for projection selection; 5) tool for custom maps; 6) spatial interpolation tool; 7) dual layer mapping tool; 8) overlays data mapping e.g. Bing and OSM river networks etc.; 9) data Calculator to perform Mathematical and logical functions over gridded or vector datasets; 10) upstream selection and user created polygon tools for data spatial aggregation and analysis. New data and features to be added: i) high resolution remote sensing data; ii) local hydroclimatic and social data; iii) interactive tool for submitting new data with user and superuser capabilities.

Figure 2: SESTRA-RIMS training workshop in Moron, Northern Mongolia.